

LIBRARY STUDENT ASSISTANTS' WORKLOAD AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Library Student Assistants' Workload and their Academic Performance

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Abstract

Student assistants play an important role in the smooth operation of the library for effective and efficient delivery of services to users. This descriptive-regression research design was utilized to determine whether student assistants' library workload has a significant influence on their academic performance. It involved 100 academic library student assistants from Regions 11 and 12, who were selected using Purposive and Universal Sampling techniques. A well-structured and self-made questionnaire was used to gather data from the respondents who worked in the library for more than two semesters. Mean scores and simple linear regression analysis were utilized to interpret and analyze all the data gathered. Results showed that the level of library student assistant's workload was not significantly related to the level of their academic performance. It also revealed that the student workload could not significantly influence student academic performance. Thus, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis. One of the recommendations is that students' assistants should develop effective time-management strategies to balance work responsibilities with academic commitments to improve academic performance.

Keywords: *library and information science, workload, academic performance, quantitative study, Philippines*

Introduction

Student assistants have a crucial role in the library, contributing to its smooth operation while offering worthwhile learning opportunities. They support the library's operations by performing various tasks such as cataloging, shelving books, assisting patrons, and managing circulation desks. Typically, student assistants work a set number of hours per day, which varies according to the library's needs. However, balancing their responsibilities as library assistants—encompassing their assigned tasks and working hours—and their academic commitments remains an important subject for this study.

Students working as library assistants face both challenges and benefits in balancing their work and academic responsibilities. In the United States, studies by Tetteh and

Attigbo (2019) and Mellili, Mitola, and Hunsaker (2016) highlight that combining work and study often leads to less time for studying, negatively impacting academic performance. Similarly, in the Philippines, Filipino students struggle with heavy workloads, leading to stress, anxiety, and a higher risk of dropping out, as noted by Godio et al. (2022) and Pedroso et al. (2023). However, there are also benefits. In Canada, Benjamin and McDevitt (2018), along with Wats and Mitola (2017) and Hall (2020), found that working helps students develop valuable time management and organizational skills.

In other global contexts, such as India, students working fewer hours (1-2 hours) manage their schedules better than those working more hours (4-5 hours), according to Kaviyarasi and Balasubramanian (2018). Studies from Cambodia and China by Tessema, Ready, and Astanie (2016), Daroliaa (2014), and Nath (2021) show that moderate working hours (1-2 hours daily) do not significantly impact GPA and can sometimes even improve it. At the University of Southern Mindanao and Central Mindanao University, many working students manage to graduate despite their hectic schedules. However, those unable to balance work and study often face academic difficulties and higher dropout risks, as observed by Derayunan et al. and Ulanday & Toquero (2024).

The above related studies motivated the researcher to conduct a study which examined the issues faced by library student assistants who struggled to balance job and study commitments. This study aimed to provide empirical evidence and theoretical insights into the various elements that influence the academic difficulties experienced by individuals who are simultaneously engaged in work and pursuing their education. Furthermore, this research would provide advantages not only for those who are simultaneously employed and pursuing education but also for educational institutions that cater to this specific group of students.

Research Questions

The aimed of this study was to determine whether student assistants' library workload had a significant effect on academic performance. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of academic library student assistants' workload in terms of
 - 1.1. number of working hours per day; and
 - 1.2. assigned tasks?
2. What is the level of academic performance of library student assistant?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of library student assistant's workload and their level of academic performance?
4. Can library student assistant's workload significantly affect the student assistant's academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-regression research design was employed in this study using the survey questionnaires. Descriptive research deals with the intention of describing the characteristics of people, situations, or groups as well as the frequency with which specific phenomena occur. More specifically, it helps to answer the what, when, and where, and how questions regarding the research problem rather than the why (Siedlecki, 2020). Meanwhile, regression approach is a non-experimental method for predicting and explaining the relationship between variables (Seeram, 2019). Coyle (2012) explained that applying regression approach could help the researcher to uncover interacting factors and the nature of the interaction allowing the researcher to make predictions based on the discovered relationships. In this study, this research design was employed to determine whether workload measures in terms of working hours and assigned tasks can significantly influence the academic performance of student assistants.

Participants

The respondents of this study were consisted of 100 student assistants from Regions 11 and 12. These student assistants were required to have at least two (2) semesters of experience working in the library, regardless of their enrolled academic program. They were selected based on the following inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. The criteria for the inclusion of the respondents were the following: (1) must have at least two semesters of experience as a student assistant in academic library regardless of program enrolled and (2) must be currently employed in academic library. The exclusion criteria were as follows: (1) student assistant in academic library outside Regions 11 and 12. (2) student assistants who have not completed two (2) semesters yet. (3) student assistants who have work for more than 2 years but not currently employed in academic library. (4) student assistants who graduated already.

Instruments

This study employed a self-made survey questionnaire. To enhance its validity, a validator with expertise was consulted to assess and confirm the appropriateness of the questionnaire on how much time student assistants spend working per day, the tasks they do, and how well they are doing academically through general weighted average (GWA). The questionnaire was divided into three parts. In part one, the researcher collected information about how many hours per day student assistants spend at work. Part two consisted of ten (10) statements about their assigned tasks, which were answered by the respondents using a five-point Likert scale, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest. Finally, the last part, the academic performance, particularly their GWA (General Weighted Average) was obtained from the school registrar. The study carried out a pilot study to examine the soundness and dependability of the study instruments. The pilot study was used to test the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire before conducting the actual research study to allow the researcher to adjust and to modify the research instruments (Mohaddesi & Hartevelde 2020). Therefore, the researcher conducted a pilot study to the specific institution with 35 respondents. The pilot study was helpful to determine whether the questions in the survey questionnaire measure what they were intended for and if responses were elicited from those questions.

Procedure

The researchers undertook the following procedures to investigate the study: First, the researcher secured an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School, Cor Jesu College Inc. to conduct the study. Second, the researcher secured an ethical clearance from Cor Jesu College Research Ethics Committee. After securing the approved letter from the Dean of the Graduate Schools and Ethical clearance from Cor Jesu College Research Ethics Committee, the researcher contacted the head librarians through official channels, such as email or Facebook, to inquire about the availability of student assistants and the possibility of obtaining their profiles. It followed up with a formal written request outlining the purpose of the study and requesting access to the student assistants' profiles. Upon receiving approval from the head librarians, the researcher distributed a consent form along with the survey questionnaire to the identified respondents. Subsequent to their approval the link of the form was shared through facebook, and email add to the respondents. Lastly, data gathered were tallied and interpreted as a basis for analysis and findings

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the survey, the researchers ensured that the respondents voluntarily participated in the study, and that no harm inflicted to the respondents. Also, the gathered data were treated with confidentiality.

Data Analysis

To interpret and analyze all the gathered data, the following statistical tools were employed: Mean Scores was employed to determine and measure the respondent's level of workload in terms of the number of working hours and the assigned tasks. Mean score is the most common measure of central tendency and refers to the average value of a group of numbers (Asaad, 2008; Syke, Gani & Vally, 2016). Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Pearson's r is a measure of the linear relationship between two interval or ratio variables and can have a value between -1 and 1. It is the same measure as the point-biserial correlation; a measure of the relationship between a dichotomous (yes or no, male or female) and an interval/ratio variable (Burns & Grove, 2005; Polit & Beck, 2006). In this study, Pearson r was used to determine the relationship between workload in terms of working hours and assigned tasks, and their academic

performance. Lastly, Simple Linear Regression Analysis. It is a fundamental tool in statistical analysis for exploring and understanding the relationship between two continuous variables (Zou et al., 2003). In the context of the study, simple linear regression was employed to determine if the workload of student assistants influence the academic performance.

Results

The researchers presented the results of the study in four parts, namely, level of academic library student assistants' workload, library students assistants' level of academic performance, and influence of library student assistants' workload towards academic performance.

Level of Academic Library Student Assistants' Workload

Table 1 presents the data on the level of academic library students assistants' workload. Shown are the mean scores of the respondents with a corresponding descriptive rating and verbal interpretation.

Table 1. Level of Academic Library Student Assistants' Workload

<i>Indicaor</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Number of working hours per day	2.01	6-7 hours	Indicates that respondents are working long hours as working assistants.
Assigned tasks	4.16	Agree	Indicates that assigned tasks are sufficient to handle, thus allowing time to study alongside fulfilling responsibilities and fostering personal growth while working in the library
Overall	3.00	Average	Indicates that the workload of the respondents was average in terms of the number of working hours per day and assigned tasks

The result showed that the mean value of 'number of working hours per day' was 2.01 with the descriptive rating of 6-7 hours which indicates that respondents are working long hours as working assistants. In terms of the assigned tasks, 4.16 gained the highest mean value between the two which indicates student assistants agree that assigned tasks are sufficient to handle, thus allowing them to study alongside fulfilling responsibilities and fostering personal growth while working in the library. Finally, the analysis showed that the mean value for both the number of working hours per day and assigned tasks is 3.0, indicating that the respondents' workload was average in terms of both the number of working hours per day and assigned tasks. They were not overextended with long hours or an excessive task, nor were they underutilized.

Library Students Assistants' Level of Academic Performance

Table 2 presents the data on the library student assistants' level of academic performance Shown are the mean scores of the respondents with a corresponding descriptive rating and verbal interpretation.

Table 2. Library Students Assistants' Level of Academic Performance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Academic Performance	86.78	Very Satisfactory	Above average academic performance

It reveals that the academic performance of students has the mean value of 86.78 which demonstrates student assistants have very satisfactory academic performance. This result implies that they have above average academic performance while working as student assistants.

Significant Relationship Between Level of Library Student Assistants Workload and their Level of Academic Performance

Presented in Table 3 is the significant relationship between library student assistants' workload and the level of their academic performance.

Table 3. Results and Interpretation on the Significant Relationship Between Level of Library Student Assistants' Workload and their Level of Academic Performance

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Significance (Probability) Value</i>	<i>Pearson (r) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Library student assistant's workload				
level of academic performance	.434	.017	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the null hypothesis

One of the aims of the study is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of library student assistant's workload and their level of academic performance. In order to provide an answer to the problem, data were gathered and processed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation test. Results revealed that the significance (probability) value at 2-tailed is equal to .434 which

is computed to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study. This finding implies that the level of library student assistant's workload is not significantly related to the level of their academic performance. The result on the Pearson (r) which is equal to .017 further affirms the absence of such relationship and that the magnitude of the relationship is nearly zero. Thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis.

Influence of Library Student Assistants' Workload Towards their Academic Performance

Table 4 shows the regression which equation $AP = \beta_0 + \beta_1SW$ (student workload) + $C1$ was tested using simple linear regression analysis.

Table 4. *Results and Interpretation on the Influence of Library Student Assistants' Workload Towards their Academic Performance*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Significance (Probability) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Library student assistant's workload	Level of academic performance	.868	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the null hypothesis

Results from the ANOVA show that the sig-value is .868 which is found to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study. This implies that overall, the model is considered to be not significant and that the model does not fit the data. The result clearly indicates that student workload could not significantly influence student academic performance.

Discussion

Level of Academic Library Student Assistants' Workload

As to the level of academic library student assistants' workload. The result of the analysis showed that the mean value of 'number of working hours per day' was 2.01 with the descriptive rating of 6-7 hours which indicates that respondents are working long hours as working assistants. With this level of commitment, students are likely to have less time available for studying or attending classes. They may face challenges in balancing work and academic responsibilities. In the study of Muluk (2017), when students were asked how many hours they spent working on campus, two student assistants indicated they worked for 6 hours per day as they had to work long hours because their task was heavy. These individuals must work long hours to meet their demands, and their pay is adequate.

One responder stated that he worked more than 35 hours per week, or 7 hours per day, because there was still a staff shortage at his workplace. Until new employees are hired, he must do additional tasks. In terms of the assigned tasks, 4.16 gained the highest mean value between the two which indicates student assistants agree that assigned tasks are sufficient to handle, thus allowing them to study alongside fulfilling responsibilities and fostering personal growth while working in the library. These findings are consistent with the other findings of study conducted by Hasson, McKenna and Keeney (2014). Student assistants working in university libraries find that the tasks assigned to them are well balanced. This balance allows them to devote enough time to their studies while also acquiring useful work experience. These could benefit not just their academic performance but also their personal development. For example, jobs like as book shelving, patron assistance, and resource management teach students valuable skills such as organization, communication, and problem-solving (Alipio, 2020). Furthermore, the encouraging environment in the library promotes teamwork and meaningful interactions among student assistants and flexible scheduling and task distribution allow them to alter their burden accordingly (Dundes & Marx, 2016).

Finally, the analysis showed that the mean value for both the number of working hours per day and assigned tasks is 3.0, indicating that the respondents' workload was average in terms of both the number of working hours per day and assigned tasks. They were not overextended with long hours or an excessive task, nor were they underutilized. This average level of workload suggests that student assistants were generally able to manage their responsibilities effectively, maintaining a sustainable balance between their work and academic responsibilities (Mathew, 2014).

The findings of the study mentioned above is supported by the research conducted by Santoso et al. (2020), which highlighted the importance of student success in both academic and work settings. Santoso et al. (2020) emphasized that students with higher levels of self-management skills are able to effectively balance their academic and work responsibilities (workload), resulting in better performance and reduced academic stress. Self-management is an essential discipline element applied by many international students to avoid low school performance and work performance (Moirá et al. 2020). Additionally, Santoso et al. (2020) underscored the significance of reducing academic stress by ensuring a harmonious integration of work and study.

Library Student Assistants' Level of Academic Performance

As to the library student assistants' level of academic performance. It reveals that the academic performance of students has the mean value of 86.78 which demonstrates student assistants have very satisfactory academic performance. This result implies that they have above average academic performance while working as student assistants. These findings are supported by previous studies, such as Guzman and Masa (2015), which also found that student assistants maintain good academic performance while working because they can manage their workload and had good support systems in workplace (Sadique et al. 2023).

The findings above were corroborated by the study of Sadique et al (2023) which showed that most student assistants were high achievers. A more flexible work schedule contributes to higher academic performance among these students. Additionally, research by Verulava and Jorbenadze (2022) demonstrated that high-value employment motivates students to devote the necessary effort toward their studies. Their findings indicated that such employment has a favorable effect on academic performance.

Significant Relationship Between Level of Library Student Assistants Workload and their Level of Academic Performance

The study revealed that the significance (probability) value at 2-tailed is equal to .434 which is computed to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study. This finding implies that the level of library student assistant's workload is not significantly related to the level of their academic performance. The result on the Pearson (r) which is equal to .017 further affirms the absence of such relationship and that the magnitude of the relationship is nearly zero. Thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis.

The findings are supported by the study of Benjamin and McDevitt (2018) that students who work six or more hours per day have a higher-grade point average compared to those working only four hours per week. This suggests that students who work longer hours may develop better time management skills, which they then apply to their studies. Moreover, the study of Alfano and Eduljee (2014) contradicted showing that there was not a significant and strong relationship between the number of hours and student assistants' academic performance. In relation to this study the researcher was unable to find a significant relationship between hours students worked and GPA.

Additionally, working more hours might foster increased responsibility, independence, and self-confidence, all of which can contribute to improved academic performance. Moreover, despite the potential for heavier workloads to impose time constraints that might hinder academic success, the findings suggest otherwise. It turns out that workload in the library does not affect how well the student assistants do academically. Consequently, their time constraints may motivate them like deadlines, resulting in increased efficiency. Without such pressures, nonworkers and light workers may, for example, procrastinate.

Influence of Library Student Assistants' Workload Towards their Academic Performance

Results from the ANOVA show that the sig-value is .868 which is found to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study. This implies that overall, the model is considered to be not significant and that the model does not fit the data. The result clearly indicates that student workload could not significantly influence student academic performance.

There are some other studies found that the level of library student assistant's workload does not significantly influence the level of their academic performance. The above findings corroborated with the research findings of Daniel (2016) and Hawkin et al. (2015) which revealed that there was no significant relationship between workload and academic performance. It implies that students who work a few hours a week are not any more likely than those who work many hours to have a higher or lower. Furthermore, another study by Nonis et al. (2016) supported the findings that student workload does not negatively influence academic outcomes. This implies that one can argue that it is simply the study behavior that ultimately brings about the desired performance and not students' inner desires or motivations. This is supported by the widely held belief that it is hard work (i.e., workload) that results in academic success and that laziness and procrastination ultimately result in academic failure.

Additionally, a Chinese study found no general effect of part-time work on grade point average but did find that extensive hours of working reduced students' grade point average (Wang et al. 2018). Moreover, one additional aspect to consider is the concept of effective time management. It is not just about the number of hours spent studying or the volume of tasks completed, but rather how efficiently that time is utilized (Mercanlioglu, 2018). Students who can prioritize tasks, set realistic goals, and maintain a healthy balance between work and rest are likely to perform better academically, regardless of the workload. Thus, while laziness and procrastination are indeed detrimental, the ability to manage time effectively can mitigate their negative effects and contribute to overall academic success. Finding no correlation, supported by Astin's fourth postulate in his theory of student engagement, it claimed that the amount of student learning and personal development is associated with any educational program (Astin, 1999). Incorporating this postulate into the research, the theory proposes that there is no significant correlation between GPA and hours worked because students' performance is influenced not by the number of hours they work, but by the quality and amount of effort they put into achieving higher grades in their courses.

Astin's (1999) theory suggested that the quantity of time impacts personal development. This study also investigated whether the number of hours students worked affected the time they dedicated to their academics, including studying, and completing assignments. The survey results indicated no significant correlation between workload such as working hours and hours spent on academics, suggesting that regardless of how many hours students worked, there was no trend indicating that increased work hours led to either fewer or more hours devoted to academics.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that in terms of number of working hours per day, respondents were working long hours and interpreted as students are likely to have less time available for studying or attending classes. They may face challenges in balancing work and academic responsibilities. On the one hand, in terms of the assigned tasks, 4.16 is the highest mean

value, which indicates that student assistants agree that assigned tasks are sufficient to handle, thus allowing them to study alongside fulfilling responsibilities and fostering personal growth while working in the library. Workload such as working hours and assign tasks in the library does not affect how well the student assistants do academically. There are other factors such as effective time management, the supportive academic environment of the library, and motivated to do well are more influential in academic success. That part-time work does not generally affect students' academic performance, but it is hard work (i.e., workload) that results in academic success and that laziness and procrastination ultimately result in academic failure. This suggests that while working a moderate number of hours might not impact grades; working excessively can make it harder for students to do well in school. The findings highlight the importance of balancing work and study to avoid the negative effects of overworking on academic success. That the correlation between workload and academic success is complex and impacted by various factors and is not significant. The nature of assign task performed by library assistants is a key factor in determining how workload affects academic attainment. Certain tasks may necessitate only a small amount of cognitive exertion, while others may be more challenging and time-consuming, which can impact students' capacity to dedicate enough time to their academic pursuits. That the findings emphasize the crucial significance of institutional support and resources in reducing the adverse impact of workload on academic achievement. While workload is undoubtedly a not significant aspect of students' educational experiences, its direct impact on academic performance is often overstated. Factors such as time management skills, support systems, and individual differences play more substantial roles in determining students' success.

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are formulated. First, student assistants should develop effective time-management strategies to balance work responsibilities with academic commitments to improve academic performance. Second, they should establish open communication with librarians or supervisors regarding workload concerns, availability, and academic obligations for effective and efficient work performance. Third, student assistants should seek academic support services, such as tutoring, study groups, or counseling, to enhance academic performance and manage workload-related stress. Fourth, student assistants need to take responsibility by effectively planning and organizing their activities to ensure they have time for their academic work.

They should minimize social activities to prioritize their studies. This is necessary because there is only so much that employers and academic institutions can do to support them. Fifth, librarians should provide clear job expectations, responsibilities, and workload requirements to student assistants to ensure mutual understanding and alignment. Sixth, librarians should offer flexible scheduling options to accommodate student assistants' academic schedules and minimize conflicts between work and studies. Seventh, Librarians should foster a supportive work environment that prioritizes student well-being and academic success, offering resources and guidance as needed. Eight, school administrators should formulate clear guidelines for workload allocation and management to ensure that student assistants' responsibilities are reasonable and conducive to academic success. Ninth, librarians should provide training programs and professional development opportunities for student assistants to enhance their skills, effectiveness, and well-being in their roles. Tenth, school administrators should advocate for the availability of academic support services and resources that address the unique needs of student employees, promoting holistic development and success; and lastly, future researchers should conduct an in-depth study related to the study but focus on longitudinal study to examine how workload and academic performance evolve over time and the long-term implications for student success.

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